

FEATURES COMPLIANCE OF PATIENT ADHERENCE IN THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

Ikromova F. A.

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14050166>

Relevance. Today, the problem of chronic heart failure (CHF) in modern society remains socially and medically relevant due to its significant prevalence, high level of disability and mortality. The studied data from long-term studies indicate insufficient secondary prevention of CHF both at the population level and among people with a high risk of developing it. Among the reasons for this situation, a special place is given to insufficient adherence of patients to drug and non-drug therapy. Studying the attitude of patients to prescribed therapy and the degree of its compliance is a fairly new area of scientific research. The development of this direction is due to the large role of the paradigm of doctor-patient interaction, the transition from the paternalistic model to partnership relations, and the patient's awareness of his own active role in therapy.

Purpose of the study. Adaptation and implementation of medication monitoring questionnaires in the treatment of patients with CHF, and evaluation of their effectiveness in improving patient compliance.

Material and methods of research. The study included 74 patients with CHF. The mean age of the patients was 68.28 ± 0.70 years. Gender distribution: 46 women (62.2%) and 28 men (37.8%). All patients received outpatient treatment (4.36 ± 0.15 on the first days of treatment).

When interviewing patients and analyzing the contents of home first-aid kits, a significant number of available medications were identified (minimum – 2, maximum – 19). The prevailing amount of drugs even with a significant volume of prescriptions could accumulate in patients only if the medication regimen was constantly violated and they were regularly received on preferential prescriptions. In the first-aid kits of individual patients, the number of drugs for the treatment of concomitant pathology reached 18 items (on average, 8.7 ± 7.16). A survey using the Morisky–Green test found only $18.1 \pm 3.7\%$ of patients were compliant with the therapy.

Results. Observations of patients who received treatment for 3 months showed that patients in the main group had significantly higher compliance rates according to the results of the Morisky-Green scale and higher quality of life indicators compared with patients in the control group. Based on the demonstrated effectiveness, accessibility and simplicity, the proposed method can be recommended for implementation in a wide medical.

References:

1. Ab E., Denig P., Ton van Vliet, Dekke J. Reasons of general practitioners for not prescribing lipid-lowering medication to patients with diabetes: a qualitative study // BMC Family Practice.- 2009. - №1471.- P.10-24.
2. Gilutz H. Computerized Community Cholesterol Control (4C): Meeting the Challenge of Secondary Prevention // IMAJ.- 2009.- Vol. 11.- P.33-36

3. Devabhaktuni M., Bangalore S. Fixed combination of amlodipine and atorvastatin in cardiovascular risk management: patient perspectives // Vascular Health and Risk anagement. - 2009.- № 5.- P.377-387.
4. Sawada N. Persistence and compliance to antidepressant treatment in patients with depression: A chart review // BMC Psychiatry.- 2009.- Vol. 1471, № 244X.- P.9-38.
5. Lakatos P.L. Use of new once-daily 5-aminosalicylic acid preparations in the treatment of ulcerative colitis: Is there anything new under the sun? // World J Gastroenterol. - 2009.- № 15.- P.1799-1804..

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY